

UV and extractive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of Nebivolol hydrochloride in tablets

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Abstract : Three simple and cost effective spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the estimation of Nebivolol hydrochloride in bulk and pharmaceutical formations. Here Nebivolol hydrochloride exhibits maximum absorbance at 283.5 nm. The absorbance concentration plot is linear over the range of 10–65 µg/ml. The molar absorptivity is $6.4959 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with correlation coefficient of 0.999 and two colorimetric methods which are based on formation of chloroform soluble complex with water soluble dyes i.e. Bromocresol Green (BCG) and Solochrome black T (SBT) exhibiting maximum absorption at 414.7 and 515.2 nm respectively. The absorbance plots are linear over the range of 1–11 and 10–90 µg/ml respectively. The molar absorptivities are 3.6677×10^5 and $4.994 \times 10^3 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with correlation coefficient of 0.9991 and 0.9917 the different experimental parameters affecting the development and stability of the color were studied carefully and optimized. The proposed methods were applied successfully to the determination of Nebivolol hydrochloride in tablets formulation.

Keywords : Nebivolol hydrochloride, acid dye, pharmaceutical analysis.

The therapeutic efficacy and safety of β -adrenergic blockers are well known in hypertension, angina pectoris and heart failure¹. Nebivolol is a very promising β -adrenergic antagonist agent with selective β -adrenergic receptor antagonizing properties and lack of intrinsic sympathomimetic activity². Nebivolol hydrochloride (NBH) is chemically 1-(6-fluoro-chroman-2-yl)-[2-(6-fluoro-chroman-2-yl)-2-hydroxyethylamino]-ethanol hydrochloride.

In the present investigation an attempt was made to develop simple and economical spectrophotometric methods with greater precision, accuracy and sensitivity for analysis of NBH in bulk and dosage forms.

Experimental

A GBC Cintra-10 double beam UV visible spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched quartz

cells (Australia) was used in the present investigation. Analytical balance of Sartorius (basic plus), Germany was used. The chemicals used were of analytical grade. Solutions of BCG (0.1% w/v), SBT (0.1% w/v) and buffer solutions of different pH were prepared in distilled water³. NBH as generously supplied by M/s Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Ahmedabad was used as such without further purification. The commercially available tablets of NBH were procured from local market labeled to contain 2.5 mg NBH/tablet and 5 mg NBH/tablet.

Stock solution of NBH (1000 µg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of NBH in 100 ml of distilled water. Aliquots of working standard solution (100 µg/ml) were suitably diluted to give final concentrations of 10 to 65 µg/ml keeping a difference of 5 µg/ml. The calibration curve (10 to 65 µg/ml) was plotted between the concentration of the drug and absorbance and the standard curve was made at 283.5 nm. The colorimetric determination, varying quantities of working standard drug solution representing 1–11 and 10–90 µg/ml of NBH, 2 ml of dye solution (BCG or SBT), 2 ml of buffer solution (pH 2.2 for BCG or pH 4.0 for SBT) were added finally

volume made up with distilled water, transferred into separating funnel, chloroform (5 × 2 ml) was added to the separating funnel and contents were shaken for 2 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the absorbance of the chloroform layer was measured at 414.7 nm and 515.2 nm for BCG and SBT dyes respectively, then calibration curve plotted for both (1–11 µg/ml for BCG and 10–90 µg/ml for SBT). The sample solutions prepared were also treated in similar manner and the exact amount of NBH present was deduced from the calibration graph.

Table 1. Selection of suitable buffer solutions

Time (min)	Absorbances					
	BCG drug complex at different pH ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 414.7 \text{ nm}$)			SBT drug complex at different pH ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 515.2 \text{ nm}$)		
	2.2	2.8	4	2.2	2.8	4
0	1.7109	1.4139	1.3009	0.1858	0.2012	0.2549
30	1.7041	1.3995	1.2994	0.1855	0.1996	0.2554
60	1.7039	1.3992	1.2998	0.1853	0.1989	0.2544
90	1.7044	1.3904	1.2990	0.1848	0.1986	0.2539
120	1.5127	1.3896	1.1049	0.1713	0.1978	0.2541

Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and pulverized. A weighed portion of the powder equivalent to 50 mg of NBH was transferred into 50-ml standard flask containing 30 ml of distilled water and shaken using a sonicator for 15 min. The volume was adjusted to the mark with water, mixed and filtered and then proceeded as described earlier. The nominal content of the tablets was determined either from the calibration curve or using the regression equation.

Results and discussion

Determination of NBH has been done by ultraviolet spectrophotometric method at the absorption maxima 283.5 nm (Fig. 1). Drug content was determined accordingly using calibration curve. Acid-dye colorimetric technique was developed using BCG and SBT dyes⁴. The proposed method was based on addition of an amine in its ionized form to an ionized dye, yield a salt (ion-pair) that was extracted into an organic solvent such as chloroform or dichloromethane. The indicator dye was added in excess and the pH of the aqueous solution was adjusted to a value where both the amine and dye were in the ionized forms. The ion-pair was separated from the excess indicator by extraction into the organic solvent. Here aqueous solution of the drug formed color complexes with BCG and SBT, which were soluble in chloroform. BCG drug dye complex and SBT drug dye complex shows absorption maxima at 414.7 nm and 515.2 nm respectively.

Table 2. Selection of suitable dye concentrations

Time (min)	Absorbances			
	BCG drug complex at different dye con. (w/v)		SBT drug complex at different dye con. (w/v)	
	0.1%	0.2%	0.1%	0.2%
0	1.7109	1.7119	0.2549	0.2547
30	1.7041	1.7011	0.2544	0.2545
60	1.7039	1.7042	0.2544	0.2541

The stock solution was diluted with distilled water to give the drug concentration 100 µg/ml. A 2 ml portion of this diluted solution was pipette out and added to three

Table 3. Optical and regression characteristics of the proposed methods

Parameters	UV	With BCG	With SBT
λ_{max} (nm)	283.5	414.7	515.2
Beer's law	10–65	1–11	10–90
Limit ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)			
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)*	6.4959×10^3	3.6677×10^5	4.994×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ abs unit}$)*	0.0680	0.0120	0.0884
Linear regression equation ^a	$A = 0.0143C + 0.0108$	$A = 0.1001C - 0.0621$	$A = 0.0097C + 0.0087$
S_a	1.866×10^{-1}	7.283×10^{-3}	2.2166×10^{-1}
tS_a^b	4.159×10^{-1}	1.646×10^{-2}	5.242×10^{-1}
S_b	4.522×10^{-3}	1.073×10^{-3}	3.939×10^{-4}
tS_b^c	1.007×10^{-2}	2.420×10^{-3}	9.315×10^{-3}
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.9998	0.9991	0.9917

Fig. 1. UV scan of Nebivolol hydrochloride.

separating funnels. 2 ml of BCG solution and 2 ml of buffers (pH 2.2, 2.8, 4.0 and 9.0) were added to each. Shaken well and extracted with 4×2 ml of chloroform. Later the extracts were taken into 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume made up. Absorbances were measured at 414.7 nm. Same procedure was applied for the SBT then absorbances were measured at 515.2 nm. It was found that drug with BCG gave maximum absorbance at pH 2.2 and with SBT gave maximum absorbance at pH 4 (Table 1).

The same experiment as mentioned above was carried out with 0.1% and 0.2% (w/v) of the dye concentration to determine the minimum concentration of the dye required to give optimum results (Table 2). But it was found that both dyes did not show much difference in absorbances. So 0.1% w/v concentration was selected for both.

The stability of the drug dye complexes was determined individually for both the dyes (BCG and SBT). A 2 ml portion drug concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was pipette out and added to a separating funnel. 2 ml of BCG solution (0.1% w/v) and 2 ml of buffers were added to each. Shaken well and extracted with 4×2 ml of chloroform. Later the extracts were taken into 10 ml volumetric flasks and volume made up. The absorbances were measured periodically at an interval of 30, 60, 90 and 120 min at 414.7 nm. Same procedure was applied for the SBT then absorbances were measured at 515.2 nm. Finally it was

found that BCG drug complex was stable for 1 h and 30 min, whereas SBT drug complex was stable for more than 2 h (Table 1).

Under the optimized experimental conditions, calibration graphs were constructed by plotting the absorbance against the concentration. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 10–65 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for UV, 1–11 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 10–90 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for BCG and SBT dyes. Table 3 summarizes the optical characteristics and the results of statistical analysis of the experimental data such as linear regression equations, correlation coefficient, standard deviation of slope (S_b) and intercept (S_a), confidence interval of slope (tS_b) and intercept (tS_a).

The proposed methods were tested on tablet formulations, the result of analysis of commercial formulation significantly showed low values of standard deviation, standard error of mean, coefficient of variation and percentage range of error (within 95% confidence limits).

Conclusions :

The proposed methods are simple, rapid, precise and inexpensive. The methods do not require any pretreatment of the drug and tedious extraction procedure prior to its analysis. The newly developed methods are sensitive enough to enable quantitation of the drug at

low concentrations. These advantages encourage the application of the proposed methods in routine quality control analysis of NBH in pharmaceutical formulations.

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References

1. B. Dahlof, L. H. Lindholm, L. Hansson, B. Schersten, T. Ekblom and O. P. Wester, *Lancet*, 1991, **338**, 1281; M. Packer, M. R. Bristow, N. J. Cohn, W. S. Colucci, M. B. Fowler, E. M. Gilbert, M. H. Shusterman and N. Engl, *J. Med.*, 1996, **334**, 1349; S. Yusuf, R. Peto, J. Collins and P. Sleight, *Prog. Cardiovasc. Dis.*, 1985, **27**, 335.
2. J. W. Janssen, A. Van de Water, R. Xhonneux, R. S. Reneman, J. M. Van Nueten and P. A. J. Janssen, *Eur. J. Pharmacol.*, 1989, **159**, 89.
3. Indian Pharmacopoeia, 3rd ed., Vol. 2, Controller of Publications, New Delhi, 1985, A-142.
4. C. S. P. Sastry, N. Y. Petla and S. S. N. Murthy, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1993, **59**, 124; T. T. Rao, U. Viplavaprasad, T. Sivarao and C. S. P. Sastry, *Indian Drugs*, 1993, **30**, 522.